

VACCINE HESITANCY AND KNOWLEDGE OF INFANT'S CAREGIVER ON THE NATIONAL IMMUNIZATION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The vaccine hesitancy and knowledge of the infant's caregivers on the National Immunization Program (NIP) has been studied to determine the level of their hesitancy and to know their knowledge regarding the NIP. It also aims to assess the relationship of the variables which may show the factors influencing their vaccine acceptance and refusal. A descriptive correlational research design was utilized to facilitate a comprehensive assessment about the hesitancy and knowledge of the caregivers. Additionally, the correlational design allows the researcher to determine the relations of the variables. The respondents were chosen using a Convenience Sampling based on their availability and willingness to participate to ensure that the study could be conducted efficiently on the Barangays of Rural Health Unit (RHU) I of City of San Fernando, Pampanga. The researchers used standardized questionnaires which comprised 30-items questions. The data were input on Microsoft Office Excel 365 and were analyzed by the statistician using the SPSS. In knowing the association between the vaccine hesitancy and demographic profile, a Chi-square test was used since the variables were organized using enumeration and they were categorical. The results show that the sex, gender, and employment status are not associated with one another but the religion and educational status are associated with the level of vaccine hesitancy. Additionally, a Pearson- Product moment correlation technique was used to describe the relation between the knowledge of the caregivers and the vaccine hesitancy. It was found out that the caregivers have a below average knowledge about vaccines.

Keywords: *Vaccine, Vaccine hesitancy, knowledge, caregivers, national immunization program*

INTRODUCTION

Vaccine hesitancy poses a significant health issue globally. It occurs when people delay or refuse to get vaccinated, even when vaccines are available. This hesitancy makes it difficult to maintain the health of the community worldwide. The vaccines are known to be beneficial to the health, and it can prevent a lot of diseases. In addition to that, vaccines are critical to reducing childhood mortality, preventing an estimated two to three million deaths per year, the most of which occur in developing countries (Masters et al., 2018). And according to Domingues et al. (2012), vaccination stands out as one of the greatest discoveries in public health for the benefit of the general population and is one of the primary preventative methods available for a significant percentage of infectious and transmissible diseases. It was found out that immunization is important in preventing diseases during infancy and later life.

One of the programs that the government offers to lower the infant mortality rate and morbidity cases is the National Immunization Program (NIP). The NIP is regarded as the most cost effective, safety, and reliable public health programs in preventing disease and strengthening the lives of the people (World Health Organization, n.d.). It was previously known as the Expanded Program on Immunization, and originally included six vaccine-preventable illnesses: measles, tetanus, pertussis, poliomyelitis, and tuberculosis (Department of Health, 2020). It was established to guarantee that infants and children had access to recommended immunizations. In addition, the vaccines can be given to a baby younger than 12 months of age. However, vaccine hesitancy remains, particularly among infant caregivers, and it may be due to the different factors like their knowledge about the vaccines. According to Nuwarda et al. (2022), vaccine hesitancy is increasingly presenting a significant challenge to vaccination initiatives and was recognized as one of the top ten global health threats by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2019.

The vaccine hesitancy is a prevalent phenomenon worldwide because of the perceived risk versus benefits, religious beliefs, and a lack of knowledge and awareness (Sallam, 2021). One of the reasons children receive their vaccinations later or parents put off receiving their children's vaccinations longer is parental hesitation. According to the studies, 77% of parents surveyed expressed worry about one or more childhood vaccines (Mckee & Bohannon, 2016). Furthermore, vaccine hesitancy persists in some countries, despite the availability of informational resources and vaccination initiation campaigns facilitated by health professionals. Moreover, the lack of trust in vaccinations has come to be recognized as a hindrance to the success of immunization campaigns. Hence, vaccine hesitancy is thought to be the cause of declining vaccine coverage and an increased risk of vaccine-preventable disease outbreaks and epidemics (Dubé et al., 2013).

In the Philippines, nurses are deployed in the community to ensure that children in their assigned units are properly immunized before they turn one-year-old. Despite several immunization initiatives, many children remain unprotected and susceptible to life-threatening vaccine-preventable infections. Thus, recognizing the barriers that have prevented parents from receiving comprehensive and timely immunization is critical,

particularly for nurses, who are the major program advocates in the community (Ridad, 2019). According to Amit (2022), although these vaccinations are available, countries still face a number of obstacles, such as vaccine hesitancy and anti-vaccination attitudes, a limited global supply, and ineffective vaccine deployment.

Due to the news about the negative impact of the vaccines, particularly the issues regarding Dengvaxia, many Filipinos are afraid of vaccinating their children. According to Arceo et al. (2021), the Philippines has been recently going through a vaccination scare because of the associated danger and side effects of the Dengvaxia vaccine. In the Philippines, there are approximately 19 deaths confirmed of vaccinated children with Dengvaxia (Magal et al., 2021), and the impact of that accident made the parents have a misunderstanding regarding the vaccines that came from the Rural Health Unit (RHU). In line with that, the vaccine hesitancy has increased because of the misunderstanding about the vaccines. And a significant number of parents acknowledge that they have doubts and worries regarding immunizations for their children (Mckee & Bohannon, 2016). The purpose of the study is to poll mothers in the province of Pampanga, Philippines on their reluctance to vaccinate their children, and to investigate potential issues related to the delay in immunizing their children.

Vaccinations are widely recognized as the most effective intervention for preventing a variety of diseases globally; yet, there are aspects that may influence the decision-making of infants' parents or caregivers. The children's ability to obtain the vaccination at the appropriate time is impacted by parental hesitation. This results in delays, rejections, and a higher chance for the children to get various diseases that could stunt their development. Due to people's misinformation, the study attempts to find out why, in spite of evidence-based information from various health organizations, parental reluctance persists. Although these studies are similar in that they examine vaccination initiatives in the Philippines and highlight the importance of vaccination in preserving public health.

The researchers study is about vaccine hesitancy and how reluctant caregivers are to vaccinate their children with the recommended vaccines. Additionally, they both study how hesitant they are about the vaccines and what the level of knowledge of the caregivers is when it comes to vaccines. On the other hand, the researcher study focuses only on the National Immunization Program (NIP), while the other study focuses on the COVID-19 vaccines, Dengvaxia, or does not have a specific vaccine focus. The importance of focusing on specific vaccines greatly helps the researchers understand their reluctance and knowledge regarding the NIP vaccines. Their decision to focus on specific vaccines helps their research be unique. Furthermore, their study found that caregivers have a low hesitancy about vaccines, which is similar to the other studies. In contrast, their study found that caregivers have a low level of knowledge, which differs from the other studies that show caregivers have a high level of knowledge about vaccines.

Review of Literature

Vaccine Hesitancy

Vaccine hesitancy, defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as "the reluctance or refusal to vaccinate despite the availability of vaccines," is a barrier to increased coverage that has gained significant attention in recent years from the media and public health researchers (Kennedy, 2020). Also, it was described as an evolving term in socio-medical literature that refers to a vaccine decision-making strategy (Kumar et al., 2016). Furthermore, vaccine hesitancy is an escalating worldwide challenge that is exacerbated by the spread of rumors and misinformation regarding vaccines (Wiyeh et al., 2018). The decrease in vaccination rates and the rise in the likelihood of vaccine-preventable disease outbreaks and epidemics are thought to be caused by vaccine hesitancy (Dube et al., 2013).

This phenomenon poses a significant risk of undoing the progress achieved through vaccination efforts. According to Eve Dubé et al. (2010), vaccine hesitancy is accountable for the low vaccine rate, and contributes to the risk of vaccine-preventable illness such as outbreaks, and epidemics. Moreover, according to the WHO (2015), 1 to 5 of the children have not yet acquired routine life-saving immunization, and 1.5 million of children died because of diseases that can be prevented by the vaccines.

Knowledge

The knowledge of Infants Caregivers about NIP has a direct effect on the parents decision about infant immunization that can possibly cause the vaccination delays and caregiver refusal. According to Almutairi et al. (2021), it suggests that parents' beliefs and knowledge regarding immunizing their children may have an impact on their practices. A child's health may benefit from vaccine delay if there is sufficient knowledge to support this. Greater knowledge and attitude were correlated with the mother's age, occupation, level of education, and family structure. The caregivers demographic profile, specifically their educational attainment may also have an impact on their understanding about vaccinations, which could result in vaccine hesitation. According to Migriño et al. (2020), caregivers' educational backgrounds and religious beliefs may have an impact on vaccine reluctance.

Infant's Caregiver

Infant caregivers are responsible for looking after the babies during their crucial first year of growth and development. They prioritize the physical, emotional and social development as well as the needs of the infants. These caregivers may work in their own homes, at the homes of their clients, or in childcare centers (Finn, 2012). Furthermore, the emotional bond between an infant and their caregiver, whether the mother or daycare provider, is essential to the child's development. In addition to that, consistent and loving care builds trust, which is the foundation for a child's emotional well-being (Bornstein et al., 2016). Bromer and Henly (2004), explains that childcare providers can act as helpers for families, offering advice and support.

National Immunization Program

The Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) that is known today as National Immunization Program (NIP) began in 1976 to allow infants or child, and the caregivers to have access to the recommended vaccines that will prevent diseases (Department of Health, 2020). According to Tilman et al. (2020), the NIP is a worldwide initiative that is universally accessible and free for all individuals globally. Furthermore, the goal is to increase the percentage of immunized individuals, and decrease the percentage of acquired diseases that can be prevented by the vaccines under NIP. In line with that, this program is free which can protect infants or children from diseases (Department of Health and Aged Care, 2023).

Based to the WHO (2024), four decades ago there are only six childhood vaccines that can prevent diseases wherein the vaccines are: Bacillus Calmette-Gerin (BCG), Diphtheria, Pertussis, Tetanus, Polio, and Measles. As the years passed by, additional vaccines were included, and as of now there are already 13 vaccines antigen recommended by the WHO which are as follows: BCG, Diphtheria, Pertussis, Tetanus, Haemophilus Influenzae type B (Hib), Hepatitis B (Hepa B), Polio, Measles, Rubelle, Pneumococcal disease (PNC), Rotavirus (Rota), Human Papillomavirus (HPV), and COVID-19. The program is continuous to prevent diseases that can endanger someone's life, and this program constantly strives for the better health of all the communities.

Research Questions

1. How may the respondents be described in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Educational Status
 - d. Religion
 - e. Employment Status
2. What is the level of knowledge towards vaccines?
3. What is the level of vaccine hesitancy of the infant's caregiver?
4. Is there a significant association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between level of vaccine hesitancy and knowledge?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative research design was used specifically, the descriptive correlational design. This approach utilizes surveys to systematically collect and analyze numerical data in order to achieve two key goals. One goal is to describe the characteristics of vaccine hesitancy among respondents categorized by their profiles. The other goal is to

explore the relationship between these levels of hesitancy and the knowledge of the caregivers regarding vaccines. By utilizing a descriptive correlational design, the study can identify the different levels of hesitancy and investigate how caregiver knowledge might be connected to a respondent's hesitancy towards vaccination.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in selected barangays under Rural Health Unit 1 (RHU 1) in the City of San Fernando, Pampanga. The name of the affiliated institution will not be mentioned, as formal permission for identification was not obtained.

Sampling Method and Respondents

This study utilized a convenience sampling technique that involves choosing participants according to their availability and willingness to participate. While this method offers logistical efficiency and feasibility, it may limit the generalizability of the findings due to potential selection bias. The respondents are the caregivers of infants residing in the selected barangays of RHU 1 who are willing to participate. Demographic profiles such as age, sex, educational attainment, religion, and employment status were gathered to describe the characteristics of the participants and give ideas to analyze possible patterns in vaccine hesitancy.

Data Gathering

1. Prior to the data collection process, the researchers will undergo an institutional ethics review conducted by the University of the Assumption Research Ethics Board (UA-REB). Upon approval from the board, the study will proceed.
2. A letter will be forwarded to the Vice-President for Academic Affairs (VPAA), directed to the Dean of the College of Nursing and Pharmacy for the approval of the chosen respondents in the study.
3. Once permitted, the distribution of the instruments, together with the bilingual informed consent form will be conducted face-to-face, approximately one month will be allotted for the collection of data.
4. The respondents will provide responses to the bilingual informed consent and questionnaires with the guidance of the researchers. The study will include only respondents who have agreed and answered the questionnaires.
5. The researchers will then compile the gathered data, ensuring the maintenance of privacy and confidentiality throughout the duration of the study.
6. The collected data will exclusively be utilized for the research study only and permission was granted by respondents for the researchers to access data and information directly from them.

Research Instruments

The data were collected using two standardized and validated instruments: (1) Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) developed by Cao et al. (2023) this instrument assesses the vaccine hesitancy among caregivers of children under three years of age. It includes

ten (10) items created on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree.” The tool demonstrated acceptable internal consistency, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.80. (2) Knowledge on Childhood Vaccination Questionnaire developed by Mukhtar et al. (2022), this measures caregivers’ knowledge regarding childhood vaccination. It comprises ten (10) items with response options; “yes,” “no,” and “unsure.” The instrument was psychometrically validated among 110 health sciences students and yielded a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.896, indicating high reliability. The first part of the complete questionnaire gathered demographic data, The second part included ten (10) items with “yes” or “no” responses on general vaccine attitudes. In total, the questionnaire contained 30 items. Authorization to use the research instruments was secured through electronic correspondence with the respective original authors.

The questionnaire was distributed using pen and paper, allowing the respondents to conveniently answer at their desired time and enabling the researchers to conduct in-person surveys. The responses given by the respondents to the questionnaire took between ten and fifteen minutes to complete.

Data Analysis

The demographic profile of the respondents-caregivers of infants in the National Immunization Program (NIP) within the covered barangays of RHU I were organized and presented using frequency and percent distributions. Also, in order to describe the level of knowledge and level of vaccine hesitancy for both parts of the used instrument, frequency and percent distributions were also used. To further describe the variables, means and standard deviations were also determined.

The following arbitrary scales were used to describe and interpret the levels of vaccine hesitancy on vaccines:

A. Part 1 Measure of Vaccine Hesitancy

Range of Scores	Adjectival Ratings
0-1	VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL
2-3	HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL
4-5	MODERATE HESITANCY LEVEL
6-7	LOW HESITANCY LEVEL
8-10	VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL

B. Part 2 Measure of Vaccine Hesitancy

Range of Scores	Adjectival Ratings
1.00-1.79	VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL

1.80-2.59	HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL
2.60-3.39	MODERATE HESITANCY LEVEL
3.40-4.19	LOW HESITANCY LEVEL
4.20-5.00	VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL

Bloom’s Cut Off Categories Used to Interpret the Scores on Knowledge of Vaccine

Range of Scores	Category
8-10 (80%-100%)	HIGH LEVEL
6-7.9 (60%-79%)	MODERATE LEVEL
<5.9 (<60%)	LOW LEVEL

In determining association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile, Chi-Square test was applied since the variables were organized using enumeration and are categorical.

Pearson-product Moment Correlation technique was employed to describe the relationship between knowledge regarding vaccine and vaccine hesitancy. Data for the said variables were expressed in interval or ratio scale using raw scores and the mean scores on vaccine hesitancy.

Scope and Limitations

The data collection was conducted in three barangays under RHU 1 specifically those with the largest population. Despite this, the study achieved 84% out of 100% although a significant percentage of potential respondents declined to participate in the study. Due to ethical considerations and the informed consent process, the researchers could not force participation. Additionally, the study’s quantitative nature limits the exploration of caregivers’ deeper opinions or perceptions about vaccines. A qualitative approach could have provided richer insights into the respondents' views on vaccination.

RESULTS

Results are presented based on the sequence of the following: (1) demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: age, sex, educational status, religion, and employment status; (2) level of knowledge towards vaccine; (3) level of vaccine hesitancy of the infant’s caregiver; (4) significant association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile; (5) significant relationship between level of vaccine hesitancy and knowledge.

Research Question 1: How may the respondents be described in terms of: (a) age, (b) sex, (c) educational status, (d) religion, (e) employment status?

Table 1a.

Sex of Respondents - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

	Frequency (Number of Respondents)	Percent (%)
Male	37	14.5
Female	218	85.5
Total	255	100.0

The sample consisted of 255 participants, with 85.5% being female and 14.5% being male.

Table 1b.

Age of Respondents - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

	Frequency (Number of Respondents)	Percent (%)
18-25 (young-adult)	89	34.9
26-44 (adult)	149	58.4
45-59 (middle-age)	17	6.7
Total	255	100.0

The sample consisted of 255 participants. The 18-25 (young-adult) age range comprises (34.9%), followed by the 26-44 (adult) age range which represented the largest portion of the sample (58.4%). The fewest participants which have (6.7%) belong to the 45-59 age range.

Table 1c.

Religion of Respondents - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

	Frequency (Number of Respondents)	Percent (%)
Catholic	219	85.9

Non-Catholic	36	14.1
Total	255	100.0

The table comprises 255 participants, majority of it belongs to the catholic groups which has 85.9% and non-Catholic groups which has 14.1%.

Table 1d.

Educational Status of Respondents - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

	Frequency (Number of Respondents)	Percent (%)
Elementary	66	25.9
Highschool	160	62.7
College Graduate	8	3.1
Undergraduate	21	8.2
Total	255	100.0

Among these different groups, high school got the highest percentage which is 62.7%. Followed by elementary which has 25.9%. The undergraduates which have 8.2%. Least were college graduates with 3.1%.

Table 1e.

Employment Status of Respondents - Caregivers of Infants in National Immunization Program

	Frequency (Number of Respondents)	Percent (%)
Employed	41	16.1
Unemployed	214	83.9
Total	255	100.0

The table shows employed respondents got 16.1% and unemployed respondents got the highest percentage which is 83.9%.

Research Question 2: What is the level of knowledge towards vaccines?

Table 2a.

Level of Knowledge on Vaccine - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

Range of Scores	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
8-10 (80%-100%)	HIGH LEVEL	58	22.7
6-7.9 (60%-79%)	MODERATE LEVEL	14	5.5
<5.9 (<60%)	LOW LEVEL	183	71.8

The table above shows that 183 (71.8%), the majority of the respondents fall into the category of low level of knowledge regarding the vaccine followed by 58 respondents (22.7%) of having high level of knowledge. Then, 14 respondents (5.5%) revealed a moderate level of knowledge.

Research Question 3: What is the level of vaccine hesitancy of the infant's caregiver?

Table 3a.

Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Range of Scores	Adjectival Ratings	Frequency	Percent (%)
0-1	Very High Hesitancy Level	59	23.1
2-3	High Hesitancy Level	38	14.9
4-5	Moderate Hesitancy Level	36	14.1
6-7	Low Hesitancy Level	36	14.1
8-10	Very Low Hesitancy Level	86	33.7
Total:		255	100.0
Mean Score: 5.04 (Low hesitancy), Standard Deviation: 3.52			

Table 3a shows that 36 (14.1%) respondents had a Low Hesitancy Level and 86 (33.7%) respondents had a Very Low Hesitancy Level for the immunization of infants. Out of 255 respondents, 36 (14.1%) had a moderate level of hesitation, 38 (14.9%) had a high level of hesitation, and 59 (23.1%) had a very high level of hesitation.

Table 3b.*Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Question*

Range of Scores	Adjectival Ratings	Frequency	Percent (%)
1.00-1.79	Very High Hesitancy Level	5	2.0
1.80-2.59	High Hesitancy Level	21	8.2
2.60-3.39	Moderate Hesitancy Level	97	38.0
3.40-4.19	Low Hesitancy Level	80	31.4
4.20-5.00	Very Low Hesitancy Level	52	20.4
Total:		255	100.0
Mean Score: 3.4110 (Low hesitancy), Standard Deviation: .77543			

Table 3b reveals that of the 255 respondents, 53 (20.4%) had very low hesitancy toward the vaccine, while 80 (31.4%) have low hesitancy. Furthermore, 97 (38.0%) respondents had a moderate degree of reluctance, 21 (8.2%) had a high level, and 5 (2.0%) had a very high level.

Table 3c.*Knowledge of the Infant's Caregivers on Vaccines*

Range of Scores	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
8-10 (80%-100%)	HIGH LEVEL	58	22.7
6-7.9 (60%-79%)	MODERATE LEVEL	14	5.5
<5.9 (<60%)	LOW LEVEL	183	71.8

Table 3c shows that 183 (71.8%) of the respondents knew very little about the NIP. 58 (22.7%) had a high level of knowledge, while 14 (5.5%) had a moderate level of knowledge about the vaccines.

Research Question 4: Is there a significant association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile?

Association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile of the Infant's caregiver using Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Table 4a.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Age - Caregivers of Infants in NIP using the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Age	0-1 very high hesitan cy level	2-3 high hesitan cy level	4-5 modera te hesitan cy level	6-7 low hesitan cy level	8-10 low hesitan cy level	Tot al	Pears on Chi- square value	p- valu e	Interpre- tation
18- 25	25	9	10	12	33	89	7.268	.508	There is no associati on between the vaccine hesitanc y and the age of the infants care
26- 44	29	25	23	22	50	149			
45- 59	5	4	3	2	3	17			
Tot al	59	38	36	36	86	255			

The table above shows there is no association with a p-value of 0.508 > 0.05.

Table 4b.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Sex - Caregivers of Infants in NIP using the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Sex	0-1 very high hesitan cy level	2-3 high hesitan cy level	4-5 modera te hesitan cy level	6-7 low hesitan cy level	8-10 low hesitan cy level	Tot al	Pears on Chi- suar e value	p- valu e	Interpre- tation
Male	13	7	7	3	7	37	7.789	.10 0	There is no associati on between vaccine hesitanc y and the sex of the
Fema le	46	31	29	33	79	218			
Total	59	38	36	36	86	255			

The table above shows that there is no association with a p-value of $0.100 > 0.05$.

Table 4c.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Educational Status - Caregivers of Infants in NIP using the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Educational Status	0-1 very high hesitan cy level	2-3 high hesitan cy level	4-5 moder ate hesitan cy level	6-7 low hesitan cy level	8-10 low hesitan cy level	Total	Pears on Chi- suar e value	p- valu e	Interpre- tation
Elementary	24	10	13	5	14	66	23.348	.025	There is association between vaccine hesitancy and educational status of infants caregiver
High School	30	28	20	24	58	160			
College Graduate	1	0	1	2	4	8			
Under-graduate	4	0	2	5	10	21			
Total	59	38	36	36	86	255			

The table above shows that there is an association between the vaccine hesitancy and the educational status of the infant's caregiver with a p-value of $0.025 < 0.05$.

Table 4d.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Religion - Caregivers of Infants in NIP using the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Religion	0-1 very high hesitan cy level	2-3 high hesitan cy level	4-5 modera te hesitan cy level	6-7 low hesitan cy level	8-10 low hesitan cy level	Total	Pears on Chi- suar e value	p- valu e	Interpre- tation

Catholic	44	31	29	33	82	219	14.993	.005	There is association between vaccine hesitancy and religion of infants caregiver
Non Catholic	15	7	7	3	4	36			
Total	59	38	36	36	86	255			

The table above shows association between the vaccine hesitancy and the religion of the infant's caregiver with a p-value of $0.005 < 0.05$.

Table 4e.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Employment Status - Caregivers of Infants in NIP using the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions

Employment Status	0-1 very high hesitancy level	2-3 high hesitancy level	4-5 moderate hesitancy level	6-7 low hesitancy level	8-10 low hesitancy level	Total	Pearson Chi-square value	p-value	Interpretation
Employed	5	10	9	3	14	41	9.206	.056	There is no association between vaccine hesitancy and employment status of infants caregiver
Un-employed	54	28	27	33	72	214			
Total	59	38	36	36	86	255			

The table above shows that there is no association between the vaccine hesitancy and the employment status of the infants' caregiver with a p-value of $0.056 > 0.05$.

Association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile of the Infant's caregiver using Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions

Table 5a.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Age using the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

Age	1.00-1.79 VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	1.80-2.59 HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	2.60-3.39 MODERATE HESITANCY LEVEL	3.40-4.19 LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	4.20-5.00 VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	Total	Pearson Chi-square value	p-value	Interpretation
18-25	2	9	35	26	17	89	8.941	.347	There is no association between the vaccine hesitancy and the age of the infants care
26-44	3	10	51	52	33	149			
45-59	0	2	11	2	2	17			
Total	5	21	97	80	52	255			

The table above shows that there is no association between the vaccine hesitancy and age of infants' caregiver with a p-value of .347 > 0.05.

Table 5b.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Sex using the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

Sex	1.00-1.79 VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	1.80-2.59 HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	2.60-3.39 MODERATE HESITANCY LEVEL	3.40-4.19 LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	4.20-5.00 VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	Total	Pearson Chi-square value	p-value	Interpretation
Male	1	5	18	9	4	37	5.500		

Female	4	16	79	71	48	218		.240	There is no association between vaccine hesitancy and the sex of the infants caregiver
Total	5	21	97	80	52	255			

Table 5b shows that there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and sex of infant caregivers with a p-value of 0.240 > 0.05.

Table 5c.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Educational Status using the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

Educational Status	1.00-1.79 VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	1.80-2.59 HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	2.60-3.39 MODE RATE HESITANCY LEVEL	3.40-4.19 LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	4.20-5.00 VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	Total	Pearson Chi-square value	p-value	Interpretation
Elementary	2	7	30	17	10	66	15.341	.223	There is no association between vaccine hesitancy and the Educational Status of the
High school	3	12	57	55	33	160			
College Graduate	0	0	3	0	5	8			

							caregiver
Undergraduate	0	2	7	8	4	21	
Total	5	21	97	80	52	255	

Table 5c shows that there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and educational attainment of infant caregivers with a p-value of 0.223 > 0.05.

Table 5d.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Religion using the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

Religion	1.00-1.79 VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	1.80-2.59 HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	2.60-3.39 MODERATE HESITANCY LEVEL	3.40-4.19 LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	4.20-5.00 VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	Total	Pearson Chi-square value	p-value	Interpretation
Catholic	1	15	79	75	49	219	30.168	.000	There is association between vaccine hesitancy and the religion of caregiver
Non-Catholic	4	6	18	5	3	36			
Total	5	21	97	80	52	255			

Table 5d shows that there is an association between vaccine hesitancy and religion of infant caregivers with a p-value of 0.000 > 0.05.

Table 5e.

Vaccine Hesitancy and Employment Status using the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions - Caregivers of Infants in NIP

Employment Status	1.00-1.79 VERY HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	1.80-2.59 HIGH HESITANCY LEVEL	2.60-3.39 MODERATE HESITANCY LEVEL	3.40-4.19 LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	4.20-5.00 VERY LOW HESITANCY LEVEL	Total	Pearson Chi-square value	p-value	Interpretation
Employed	1	0	15	18	7	41	6.816	.146	There is no association between vaccine hesitancy and the employment status of caregiver
Unemployed	4	21	82	62	45	214			
Total	5	21	97	80	52	255			

Table 5e shows that there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and employment status of infant caregivers with a p-value of $0.146 > 0.05$.

Research Question 5: Is there a significant relationship between level of vaccine hesitancy and knowledge?

Table 6a.

Relationship Between Vaccine Hesitancy using the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Question and Knowledge

Bivariates	Pearson r	Interpretation of Pearson r	of p-value	Interpretation of p-value
Vaccine Hesitancy and Knowledge	.641**	Highly correlated	.000	There is a significant relationship

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6a shows a significant link between vaccine hesitancy and knowledge, demonstrating a high correlation with a value of (r= .641, p-value =.000) utilizing the vaccine hesitancy survey questions and knowledge.

Table 6b.

Relationship Between Vaccine Hesitancy using the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Survey Questions and Knowledge

Bivariates	Pearson r	Interpretation of Pearson r	of p-value	Interpretation of p-value
Vaccine Hesitancy and Knowledge	.615**	Highly correlated	.000	There is a significant relationship

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6b presents a significant relationship between vaccine hesitancy and knowledge, indicating a strong correlation, with a result of (r= .615, p-value =.000) using the likert-scale questions and knowledge.

DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile

A study by Stephens et al. (2009) investigates gender disparities in parenting techniques and how they impact the parent-child connection. This study shows that mothers tend to spend more time with their children and they are more likely to be seen as caregivers. In line with that, women have more caring characteristics than men, and they are the ones who spend more of their time at home. Hence, they are the primary caregivers. Furthermore, in our culture as Filipinos, women are traditionally seen to be the one who take care and manage their household and their children that is why they

are called “housewives”. Lastly, men are known to be the “padre de pamilya” or the provider of the family therefore they spend most of their days at work.

It was found out that the most caregivers were found to be between the ages of 26 and 44. This could be because the reproductive age range is 26 to 44 years old. According to Mehta et al. (2020), for many, the early thirties to forties of age are the most intense and challenging of their lives. During this stage of life, most adults must balance the competing demands of advancing in a chosen career, maintaining an intimate relationship, and caring for children. One work of Bbaale (2013) suggests a possible advantage for Catholic families. The study indicates a higher percentage of Catholic children (56%) were fully immunized compared to other religions. When it comes to vaccines, Catholics are generally affected by the principles and teachings of their religion. Moreover, the majority of participants in our study were Catholic, as Catholicism has a significant influence in the Philippines, compared with other religions.

It was found out that most of the caregivers finished high school and this may be because of financial constraints, and the sudden teenage pregnancy. According to Golston (2022), many students cannot continue their studies after high school because college is too expensive. Furthermore, a sudden teenage pregnancy contributes to the fact that the majority of respondents are high school graduates, which could be due to the pregnancy interfering with their ability to continue their education. Based on the study of Mohr et al. (2019), lower education levels increase the case of teenage pregnancy. To add, insufficient understanding about the implications and consequences of early pregnancy may lead individuals to make uninformed decisions, resulting in higher rates of early pregnancy, which can negatively affect their educational status.

A study of Gao et al. (2022), suggests that unemployed parents, who are statistically more likely to be mothers, may have the availability to care for their infants compared to employed parents who need to allocate time to work. Unemployed individuals often have more flexibility in their schedules, allowing them to stay at home and attend to childcare responsibilities. This pattern can be attributed to the greater amount of time available to unemployed individuals, as they are not engaged in formal employment activities.

Level of knowledge towards vaccines

Based on the results, respondents fall into the category of having a low level of knowledge regarding the vaccine. According to DeWalt and Hink (2009), low literacy parents were less educated about their children's health and engaged in fewer helpful activities for them. Parents' vaccination knowledge may impact their practice. Major barriers to high vaccination coverage among children include a lack of knowledge or information on vaccination, low levels of awareness about vaccination, and misperceptions (Almutairi et al., 2021).

Level of Vaccine Hesitancy of the Infant's Caregiver

The data showed that, with a mean of 5.04, the 255 respondents showed a moderate level of hesitancy. This means that 23.1% of 255 respondents, had a very high hesitation level. Vaccinating infants in line with the program and having a low hesitation level towards vaccines were the responses that 31.4% of respondents correctly identified. On the other hand, a moderate hesitation level of respondents gave a misleading impression that vaccines can harm infants, based on the 38.0% of the respondents. According to figures tailed to 255 respondents, 38.8% of infant caregivers have a very low understanding of the vaccinations for their infants. As a result, respondents have a very poor understanding of vaccination hesitation, which causes infants to have vaccine delay. Vaccine hesitancy persists in the RHU 1 areas of City of San Fernando, Pampanga as it shows below average knowledge result in the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey. Parental decisions are essential for improving the immunization rate, ensuring compliance, and reducing the possibility of vaccination inaccuracies even if there are many reasons that may contribute to the poor immunization coverage (Arceo et al., 2021). The decision to vaccinate a child against diseases that the child may meet lies with the caregivers, even in cases where vaccines are easily accessible at healthcare facilities.

Association between vaccine hesitancy and the demographic profile

In the Vaccine Hesitancy Survey (VHS) Questions, the association between vaccine hesitancy and demographic profile are as follows: (1) a study from Bulgarie Nagase, cited by Nagase (2024), age is not a significant predictor of vaccine hesitancy. As a result, regardless of your age, your willingness to receive the vaccine is unaffected; a difference factor may influence vaccine hesitancy, but not the respondents' age; (2) there is no association between the vaccine hesitancy and the sex of the infant's caregiver. According to Nery et al. (2022), men and women were less likely to be hesitant about taking the vaccine. Therefore, in both groups, the likelihood of vaccine hesitancy decreased. Hence, vaccine hesitancy is not affected by sex of the respondents and it does not play a significant factor in vaccine hesitancy; (3) caregivers with low levels of education have experienced different barriers which result in high levels of vaccine hesitancy (Bergen, Kirkby, Fuertes, & et al., 2023). Furthermore, according to Ruiz and Bell (2022), the vaccine hesitancy is more prevalent among the non-college graduate or undergraduates. This may be because caregivers with lower education attainment are less knowledgeable about the different vaccines that can benefit their children and are prone to believe that vaccines can bring bad side effects on their children. Moreover, they are more likely to acquire the wrong information about vaccines which further contributes to their high levels of vaccine hesitancy; (4) according to Kibongani et.al. (2022), religious reasons for vaccine hesitancy have been identified in many religious groups such as the Catholics, Christians, and especially in Muslims. Muslims believe that vaccines can disturb their halal or during their Ramadan fasting periods and they consider vaccination is not allowed during their Ramadan. The reason for their refusal is that they should not enter or leave their body during Ramadan because it can break their fasting. Also, they believed that acquiring the disease is the will of God, and that having the vaccine would be against it. Lastly, the religious group is hesitant to receive the vaccination because they believe they have divine protection and that only God can heal them. Therefore, the

religion of the infants' caregivers is associated with the vaccine hesitancy because of their different beliefs and divine faith to God; (5) based on the study of Sujarwoto, Maharani, & et al. (2020), there was no relationship between employment status and vaccination hesitancy. As a result, employment status does not affect their willingness to have their vaccines for their children. To conclude, the age, sex, and employment status of the caregivers are not associated with the level of vaccine hesitancy. On contrast, it was found out that the religion and educational status of the respondents are associated with their level of vaccine hesitancy.

In the Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS) Likert Scale the results show that there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and the age of the caregiver. According to Wang et al. (2022), previous studies had not revealed any meaningful correlation. In addition, it is possible that caregivers lack expertise in caring for young or first-born children, therefore they are more likely to worry about vaccinations. Furthermore, it was found out that there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and the sex of the infant's caregiver. According to Merten et al. (2015), the usual gender-related differences in attitudes towards vaccination were not observed. Typically, men are less likely to trust vaccinations and women are more motivated to get health services for their children, but these differences were not seen in this study population. Moreover, vaccine hesitancy and educational attainment has no association to vaccine hesitancy. According to a study from Manila, Western Pacific surveillance and response journal (WPSAR) cited by Migriño et al. (2020), the study did not find any connection between vaccine hesitancy and the educational status of caregivers. Although there is a suggestion that the educational levels of caregivers may have an impact on vaccine hesitancy. Additionally, it is important to note that the level of education can both promote and hinder vaccine acceptance, depending on the specific context. Given the diverse range of factors that contribute to vaccine hesitancy, experts recommend contextualizing these determinants in each setting before implementing interventions.

The vaccine hesitancy and the employment status of the caregiver are not associated with each other. According to Bertocello et al. (2020), the research findings demonstrated that economic challenges play a significant role in influencing vaccine hesitancy, whereas there was no correlation observed between economic difficulties and outright vaccine refusal. Conversely, the study indicated that the limited educational attainment of parents, particularly mothers and fathers, was a reliable indicator of the rejection of all vaccines. Interestingly, parental education levels did not appear to have a substantial impact on vaccine hesitancy.

Besides that, the religion and vaccine hesitancy have an association. According to Andrade (2021), there are numerous religious explanations for vaccine reluctance that have been linked to the following religious groups: Protestants, Catholics, Jews, Muslims, Christians, Amish, Hinduists, and Sikhs. The vaccinations' use of non-halal components is one of the causes. Moreover, Protestants are the least likely to get immunized. Additionally, it was believed that parents who vaccinate their child would suffer a side effect as evidence that they made a mistake in their decision. Lastly, Rujis discovered that religious leaders hold varying opinions regarding vaccinations, with some avoiding

the subject altogether since they think vaccinations are widely accepted. Also, they let their members make the decision and sometimes address the negative connotation about vaccines in their religious work (Kibongani et al., 2022). To summarize, there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and caregiver gender, educational attainment, age and employment status. In contrast, religion was found to be associated with vaccine hesitancy.

Significant relationship between level of vaccine hesitancy and knowledge

It presents a significant relationship between vaccine hesitancy and knowledge, indicating a strong correlation. The higher the score, the higher the possibility for the respondents not to be hesitant. Similarly, the higher the knowledge, the higher the probability of having a low level of hesitancy. According to Voo et al., (2021), parents who are more knowledgeable about vaccinations are more likely to get their children vaccinated.

Conclusions

Vaccine hesitancy is a delay in acceptance, or refusal, of vaccines despite the availability of vaccine services and supporting evidence. Based on the results, the demographic profile of the respondents in sex reveals that females outnumber men when responding to the given questionnaire. In the population, the adults have the most responses, next is the young adult and the rest of the population with the least response is the middle-aged people.

The knowledge of the infant's caregivers on vaccines revealed that the respondents have a low level of knowledge about the National Immunization Program (NIP). Additionally, the level of knowledge towards vaccines shows that they have low levels of awareness about vaccinations and are more prone to misperceptions. Despite this lack of knowledge, the caregivers are not hesitant to vaccinate their children.

The respondents were then asked about their awareness regarding the level of vaccine hesitancy of the infant's caregiver, it reveals that respondents have a low hesitancy level while the respondents with very low hesitancy level have the highest percentage of not hesitant with the vaccine.

Regarding the association between vaccine hesitancy and demographic profile of the infant's caregiver, the study found that there is no association between vaccine hesitancy and age, sex, and employment status of the caregiver. This means that these factors do not influence the caregivers' willingness to vaccinate their children. However, the study found a significant association between vaccine hesitancy and educational status and religion.

Furthermore, the significant relationship between level of vaccine hesitancy and knowledge indicates a strong association wherein the higher the level of knowledge, the higher the possibility for the respondents not to be hesitant. To conclude, caregivers have a low level of knowledge about the National Immunization Program (NIP), but are not hesitant to vaccinate their children. Factors such as age, sex, and employment status do

not influence their willingness to vaccinate, but educational status and religion are significantly associated with vaccine hesitancy.

Recommendations

For the Community Members

Based on the results, the respondents tend to have a lower level of hesitancy, however, a result of above average knowledge regarding the vaccines indicates a further enhancement of health literacy. They might not be hesitant in receiving the vaccine for their child but they are not that knowledgeable about it. This strongly suggests that parents and caregivers of infants should increase their participation whenever there is a vaccination campaign in their community, to increase their awareness of the indications of different childhood vaccines. It recommends that they will not merely accept the vaccines, but rather to understand it deeply. Also, the researchers suggest carefully understanding the information about vaccines, this is usually presented through social media with the help of the Internet, family members, and primary care providers.

For the Community Health Nurses

As the healthcare providers are determined to have a positive effect on the clients in terms of health, the researchers suggest adding more details and expanding their significant knowledge that is evidence-based informations in providing a health education about the vaccines such as its relevance, importance, effects and proper use and administration of the vaccine to decrease the level of poor knowledge regarding the vaccines, this will increase the confidence of parents or caregivers of infants. Researchers recommend delivering learning materials such as infographics or booklets with vaccine information so that clients can better understand it.

For the Local Government Officials

The researchers suggest that in order to increase the level of knowledge, it is necessary to promote public health awareness through health promotion programs in every community and use a clear and concise words to highlight the most common misconceptions in understanding the importance of vaccines in order to address concerns and misunderstandings about various childhood vaccinations, as this is one of the most powerful influences that can encourage a large number of infant parents and caregivers. They may also propose using different media platforms, television and radio to communicate to parents and caregivers about the necessity of immunizations and to prevent any false information.

For the Nursing Educators

The researchers recommend nursing educators to create easily accessible educational materials, teach nursing students effective communication techniques, include comprehensive vaccine education into their curricula, encourage involvement in

community outreach programs, and use social media and technology to spread accurate vaccine information.

For the Future Researchers

The researchers recommend completing the total number of respondents under the barangays of RHU 1, this is to increase the accuracy and validity of the study. Since the study was only limited to only one Rural Health Unit in the City of San Fernando, Pampanga, they suggest expanding the geographic scale into provincial to incorporate more respondents and provide a study that is more reliable. Researchers also suggest extending the duration of data collection, since the questionnaires will be distributed face-to-face and there are unforeseen events such as sudden refusal in participating in the study.

For the Student Nurses

In order to effectively educate caregivers, the researchers advise student nurses to actively study about the National Immunization Program, engage in community outreach activities to increase vaccine knowledge, and use technology and social media to share accurate vaccine information.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The University of the Assumption's (UA) Research Ethics Board reviewed this study in order to assess the proposed research. Reviewing and evaluating the informed consent, survey questions, and other papers that the UA REB has mandated is the purpose of this.

Informed Consent Process, Duration of Participation, and Withdrawal Criteria

This study will use bilingual informed consent. The participant will be given an informed consent as part of the first section of the form that their personal information will be kept confidential and no personal data will be disclosed. The informed consent form will include information about the study's purpose, a summary of what the participants will be asked to undertake, and their rights and access to their own information. The participants will be given 10-15 minutes to complete the research questionnaires, and they have the right to withdraw and confirm the privacy of all information.

Risk and Inconveniences

Aside from the time spent filling out surveys, there are no significant risks or inconveniences associated with participating in the study. Only data directly relevant to the study's objectives will be collected. Any expected risks will cause respondents to discontinue the questionnaire, and appropriate referrals will be made.

Benefits of the Study

The respondent's potential benefit is the satisfaction that comes from knowing that they made a contribution to the study, especially in highlighting the critical role that caregiver knowledge plays in reducing vaccine hesitancy and assisting caregivers in increasing their knowledge of the vaccine. Furthermore, the benefit of this research to the community is to increase knowledge regarding the vaccine leading to the decrease of vaccine hesitancy. Lastly, knowing the level of hesitancy will help the researchers to know what will be the specific area they will address to use in their Health Promotion Program regarding vaccine hesitancy.

Privacy, Confidentiality, and Data Management

Before beginning data, approval will be obtained from the University of the Assumption Research Ethics Board (UA-REB). Respondents will be asked to provide informed consent. The data obtained from respondents in this survey will be kept strictly confidential to the fullest extent of the law. Individual identities will not be disclosed in any study-related reports or publications. Personal information gathered from the questionnaires will be encoded and stored separately from respondent names and other indirect identifiers. Access to respondents' personal information and other relevant data will be restricted to the researchers, their adviser, statistician, and other authorities involved in the study's completion, notably the University of the Assumption Research Ethics Board (UA-REB). After completing the questionnaire and analyzing the data, the information acquired from respondents will be moved to a password-protected file folder, and hard copies will be stored in a locked cabinet to ensure that it will not be tampered with by anybody. If the study expands or changes considerably, the researchers will seek the participants' approval again. Participants can withdraw at any moment without incurring any penalties. In the event of a breach, participants will be quickly notified, and the situation will be reported to the UA-REB.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest in any form (financial, proprietary, professional) with sponsor, the study, Co-Investigators, or the site.

REFERENCES

- Almutairi, W. M., Alsharif, F., Khamis, F., Sallam, L. A., Sharif, L., Alsufyani, A., Alshulah, F. N., & Alqasimi, R. (2021). Assessment of mothers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding childhood vaccination during the first five years of life in Saudi Arabia. *Nursing Reports*, 11(3), 506–516. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nursrep11030047>
- Amit, A. M. L., Pepito, V. C. F., Sumpaico-Tanchanco, L., & Dayrit, M. M. (2022). COVID-19 vaccine brand hesitancy and other challenges to vaccination in

- the Philippines. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 2(1), e0000165.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0000165>
- Andrade, G. (2021). Vaccine hesitancy and religiosity in a sample of university students in Venezuela. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 17(12), 5162–5167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2021.1981737>
- Arceo, E., Dizon, J. C., Chavez, M., Cordero, P. K., de Leon, M. R., de Luna, J., de Vera, T. F., Jose, J., Manalo, L.-D., & Tiongco, R. E. (2021). Knowledge, attitude, and practices of mothers from a rural community in Pampanga, Philippines toward childhood immunization: A cross sectional survey. *Vacunas*, 22(3), 167–172.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacun.2020.12.002>
- Bbaale, E. (2013). Factors influencing childhood immunization in Uganda. *Journal of Health, Population, and Nutrition*, 31(1), 118–129.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3702366/>
- Bergen, N., Kirkby, K., Fuertes, C. V., Schlothuber, A., Menning, L., Mac Feely, S., O'Brien, K., & Hosseinpoor, A. R. (2023). Global state of education-related inequality in COVID-19 vaccine coverage, structural barriers, vaccine hesitancy, and vaccine refusal: Findings from the Global COVID-19 Trends and Impact Survey. *The Lancet. Global Health*, 11(2), e207–e217. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(22\)00520-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(22)00520-4)
- Bertoncello, C., Ferro, A., Fonzo, M., Zanovello, S., Napoletano, G., Russo, F., Baldo, V., & Cocchio, S. (2020, June 5). *Socioeconomic determinants in vaccine hesitancy and vaccine refusal in Italy*. MDPI.
<https://www.mdpi.com/2076-393X/8/2/276>
- Bornstein, M. H., Putnick, D. L., & Suwalsky, J. T. D. (2016). Infant–mother and infant–caregiver emotional relationships: Process analyses of interactions in three contemporary childcare arrangements. *Infancy*, 21(1), 8–36.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/infa.12097>
- Bromer, J., & Henly, J. R. (2004). Child care as family support: Caregiving practices across child care providers. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 26(10), 941–964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2004.04.003>
- Department of Health (DOH). (2020). Immunization Program.
<https://doh.gov.ph/uhc/health-programs/immunization-program>
- Department of Health and Aged Care. (2023). Immunisation for infants and children. Australian Government.
<https://www.health.gov.au/topics/immunisation/when-to-get-vaccinated/immunisation-for-infants-and-children>
- Domingues, C. M. A. S., Teixeira, A. M. da S., & Carvalho, S. M. D. (2012). National immunization program: Vaccination, compliance and pharmacovigilance. *Revista Do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo*, 54, 22–27. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0036-46652012000700009>
- Dubé, E., Laberge, C., Guay, M., Bramadat, P., Roy, R., & Bettinger, J. A. (2013). Vaccine hesitancy: An overview. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 9(8), 1763–1773. <https://doi.org/10.4161/hv.24657>

- DeWalt, D. A., & Hink, A. (2009). Health literacy and child health outcomes: A systematic review of the literature. *Pediatrics*, 124 Suppl 3, S265-274. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2009-1162B>
- Finn, L. (2012). ECRP: Early Childhood Research & Practice. <http://ecrp.uiuc.edu/>
- Gao, M. G., & Ruan, H. (2022). Work-family policies and gender inequalities in childcare time. *Socius: Sociological Research for a Dynamic World*, 8, 23780231221142677. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23780231221142677>
- Golston, A. C. (2022, September 28). Why some high school graduates are opting out of college. <https://usprogram.gatesfoundation.org/news-and-insights/articles/understanding-why-a-growing-number-of-high-school-graduates-are-choosing-not-to-go-to-college>
- Kennedy, J. (2020). Vaccine hesitancy: A growing concern. *Pediatric Drugs*, 22(2), 105–111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40272-020-00385-4>
- Kibongani Volet, A., Scavone, C., Catalán-Matamoros, D., & Capuano, A. (2022). *Vaccine hesitancy among religious groups: Reasons underlying this phenomenon and communication strategies to rebuild trust*. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 824560. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.824560>
- Kumar, D., Chandra, R., Mathur, M., Samdariya, S., & Kapoor, N. (2016). Vaccine hesitancy: Understanding better to address better. *Israel Journal of Health Policy Research*, 5(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13584-016-0062-y>
- Magal, P., Seydi, O., Webb, G., & Wu, Y. (2021). A model of vaccination for dengue in the philippines 2016–2018. *Frontiers in Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 7. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fams.2021.760259>
- Masters, N. B., Tefera, Y. A., Wagner, A. L., & Boulton, M. L. (2018). Vaccine hesitancy among caregivers and association with childhood vaccination timeliness in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 14(10), 2340–2347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2018.1480242>
- McKee, C., & Bohannon, K. (2016). Exploring the reasons behind parental refusal of vaccines. *The Journal of Pediatric Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 21(2), 104–109. <https://doi.org/10.5863/1551-6776-21.2.104>
- Mehta, C. M., Arnett, J. J., Palmer, C. G., & Nelson, L. J. (2020). Established adulthood: A new conception of ages 30 to 45. *The American Psychologist*, 75(4), 431–444. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000600>
- Merten, S., Martin Hilber, A., Biaggi, C., Secula, F., Bosch-Capblanch, X., Namgyal, P., & Hombach, J. (2015, August 28). Gender determinants of vaccination status in children: Evidence from a meta-ethnographic systematic review. *PloS one*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4552892/>
- Migriño, J., Gayados, B., Birol, K. R. J., De Jesus, L., Lopez, C. W., Mercado, W. C., Tolosa, J.-M. C., Torreda, J., & Tulagan, G. (2020). *Factors affecting vaccine hesitancy among families with children 2 years old and younger in*

- two urban communities in Manila, Philippines. Western Pacific Surveillance and Response Journal : WPSAR*, 11(2), 20–26.
<https://doi.org/10.5365/wpsar.2019.10.2.006>
- Mohr, R., Carbajal, J., & Sharma, B. B. (2019, December 17). The Influence of Educational Attainment on Teenage Pregnancy in Low-Income Countries: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Social Work in the Global Community*. <https://doi.org/10.5590/jswgc.2019.04.1.02>
- Nagase, M. (2024). Factors associated with vaccine hesitancy against COVID-19 among adults in Europe: A descriptive study analysis applying socio-ecological framework. *BMC Research Notes*, 17, 84.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-024-06739-2>
- Nery, N., Ticona, J. P. A., Cardoso, C. W., Prates, A. P. P. B., Vieira, H. C. A., Salvador de Almeida, A., Souza, M. M. da S., Borba dos Reis, O., Pellizzaro, M., Portilho, M. M., Rosa da Anunciação, R., Victoriano, R., Oliveira dos Anjos, R., Argibay, H. D., Carmo Lima, D. O., Mesquita, I. L., Conceição, W. M., Santana, P. M., Oliveira, E. C., ... Ribeiro, G. S. (2022). *COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy and associated factors according to sex: A population-based survey in Salvador, Brazil*. *PLoS ONE*, 17(1), e0262649. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0262649>
- Nuwarda, R. F., Ramzan, I., Weekes, L., & Kayser, V. (2022). Vaccine hesitancy: Contemporary issues and historical background. *Vaccines*, 10(10), 1595. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines10101595>
- Ridad, G. S. (2019). Barriers to adherence to expanded program on immunization among parents in Ianao del Norte, Philippines. *Belitung Nursing Journal*, 5(1), 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.695>
- Ruiz, J. B., & Bell, R. A. (2022). Parental COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy in the United States. *Public Health Reports*, 137(6), 1162–1169. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00333549221114346>
- Sallam, M. (2021, February 16). COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy worldwide: A concise systematic review of vaccine acceptance rates. *MDPI*. <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-393X/9/2/160>
- Stephens, M. A. (2009). Gender differences in parenting styles and effects on the parent-child relationship. <https://hdl.handle.net/10877/3300>
- Sujarwoto, S., & Maharani, A. (2020, December). Participation in community-based health care interventions (CBHI) and its association with hypertension awareness, control and treatment in Indonesia. *PLoS one*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33370385/>
- Tilman, C. B., Martins, J. S., Mausiry, M., Cunha, M., Freitas, M. G., & Costa, C. M. M. da. (2020, May 11). The perception of population and health professionals regarding the National Immunization Program of Timor-Leste. *Health Systems and Policy Research*. <https://www.hsprj.com/abstract/the-perception-of-population-and-health-professionals-regarding-the-national-immunization-program-of-timorleste-26947.html>
- Voo, J. Y. H., Lean, Q. Y., Ming, L. C., Md. Hanafiah, N. H., Al-Worafi, Y. M., & Ibrahim, B. (2021). Vaccine knowledge, awareness and hesitancy: A cross

- sectional survey among parents residing at sandakan district, sabah. *Vaccines*, 9(11), 1348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9111348>
- Wang, Z., Chen, S., & Fang, Y. (2022, September 2). Parental willingness and associated factors of pediatric vaccination in the era of COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review and meta-analysis. MDPI. <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-393X/10/9/1453>
- Wiyeh, A. B., Cooper, S., Nnaji, C. A., & Wiysonge, C. S. (2018). Vaccine hesitancy 'outbreaks': Using epidemiological modeling of the spread of ideas to understand the effects of vaccine related events on vaccine hesitancy. *Expert Review of Vaccines*, 17(12), 1063–1070. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14760584.2018.1549994>
- World Health Organization. (n.d.). *Health promotion*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/health-promotion>